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Abstracts of Keynote Invited Lectures and Contributed Papers

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7.2 PARTICULATE MATTER EXPOSURE AND DOSE IN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS: AN AGENT-BASED MODELING APPROACH

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In urban environments, exposure to airborne particulate matter (PM) is a significant concern due to its potential adverse health effects. However, exposure estimates alone do not account for the amount of the pollutant that enters the human body through respiration. A comprehensive understanding can be achieved by calculating the intake dose, considering inhalation rate as minute ventilation (air entering the lungs per minute). (Greenwald et al. 2019; Novak et al. 2020). Such a dose provides deeper insights into the effects of activities, micro-locations, indoor-outdoor exposure, and personal characteristics on PM exposure.

An agent-based model (ABM) was created to provide a stochastic approach to modelling PM_{2.5} exposure and assessing the dose, with the outcomes published in Novak et al. (2023). This model considers various features and characteristics, such as age and gender, and their influence on selecting activities. Results from the ABM were then contrasted with real-world data from the ICARUS project, collected with wearable PM and biometric monitors. Both datasets exhibited coinciding trends, underscoring the potential accuracy and applicability of the ABM. However, discrepancies were observed in activities with the highest mean dose values, highlighting areas for refinement in the model. The ABM was expanded to incorporate agents influencing modal decision-making, impacting intake dose. Figure 1 shows the relationship between PM_{2.5} dose and outdoor PM_{2.5} concentration in the modified ABM. While non-activist agents exhibit a linear increase in mean cumulative dose with rising PM_{2.5} concentrations, the divergence of lines connecting activist agents' increasing doses at higher PM_{2.5} concentrations underscores their pronounced influence on PM_{2.5} dose as pollution levels intensify.

Figure 1: Average PM_{2.5} Dose for All Agents in the Modified ABM

Future work in the scope of the URBANOME project (urbanome.eu) will be to integrate some of the aspects explored in this study. One aim is to further validate the behavioural aspects of cyclists when choosing modality options. By using the ABM as a form of digital twin we seek to explore how behaviour, modality choices, external influences, and interactions between agents and the environment impact PM exposure and dose.

REFERENCES

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